

Supplementary Information

Immobilized hydroxymethylfurfural oxidase enables robust biocatalytic production of 2,5-furandicarboxylic acid from crude 5-hydroxymethylfurfural.

FDCA production using soluble CBM3-8BxHMFO

Enzymatic reactions with CBM3-8BxHMFO were carried out using 2.5 μM of enzyme, 6 mM HMF as substrate, and catalase in excess ($10\text{--}25 \text{ U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$). Reactions were performed at pH 8.0 and 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ while continuously aerating the solution with air at a flow rate of $9 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. After two days of reaction, an additional dose of HMF (6 mM) and catalase ($10\text{--}25 \text{ U}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) was supplied under the same conditions. Aliquots were collected daily to determine the residual enzymatic activity. Substrate consumption, intermediate accumulation, and FDCA formation were quantified by HPLC.

Figure S1. A) FDCA production with 2.5 μM CBM3-8BxHMFO and 6 mM HMF at pH 8, 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, 500 rpm, 0.6 vvm air. FDCA (blue diamonds), residual activity (green triangles). B) Enzyme stability at pH 8 and 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with air 0.6 vvm (green triangles) and without sparging (blue dots).

Figure S2: Immobilization kinetics of CBM3-8BxHMFO in Avicel® PH-200 Support.

Table 1S: Immobilizations of CBM3-8BxHMFO on microcrystalline cellulose.

Support	Avicel® PH-200	Perloza MT-100 medium
Offered activity ($\text{U} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}_{\text{support}}$)	0.146	0.106
Immobilization yield (IY%)	72	98
Recovered activity (RCA%)	16	10
Immobilized protein ($\text{mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}_{\text{support}}$)	55.8	53.1

Figure S3. Enzymatic reaction of CBM3-8BxHMFO immobilized on Perloza with 100 mM HMF at 30 °C, 500 rpm, pH 8, and 0.6 vvm air sparging. A) Concentration profiles of HMF, intermediates (FFCA and DFF), and the product FDCA. B) Residual activity of samples collected at different stages: (1) initial sample, (2) final sample, and (3) final reaction supernatant

Figure S4. (A) SDS-PAGE gel of immobilization and enzymatic reaction fractions. Lane 1: molecular weight marker (kDa); CBM3-8BxHMFO, 75.1 kDa. Immobilization on Perloza: lanes 2–5 correspond to blank, supernatant, immobilized derivative before the reaction, and immobilized derivative after the reaction, respectively. (B) Immobilized derivative CBM3-8BxHMFO on Perloza before and after the enzymatic reaction with 100 mM HMF.

Table S2. Protein content in the immobilized derivative before and after the enzymatic reaction.

	Total protein (immobilized derivative) (mg)	Protein (%)
Before	104,1	100
After	3,9	3,8

Table S3. Melting temperature values of soluble and immobilized CBM3-8BxHMFO.
Low load ($8.1 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}_{\text{support}}$), high load ($51.9 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}_{\text{support}}$) .

	Glutaraldehyde (%)	T _m (°C)
Soluble	0	49.7 ± 0.24
Immobilized derivative (low load)	0	52.5 ± 0.00
	0.25	51.5 ± 0.26
Immobilized derivative (high load)	0	53.2 ± 0.29
	0.25	52.0 ± 0.00

A

B

Figure S5: Reactor setup for the enzymatic production of FDCA. (A) Schematic representation of the 20 mL reactor configuration, including pH and temperature control, aeration system, and online pO₂ monitoring. (B) The experimental setup with the main components highlighted.

A

B

Figure S6: HPLC chromatogram of crude HMF recorded with diode-array detection (200–900 nm). (A) Spectral scan across wavelengths showing absorbance distribution of major peaks. (B) Corresponding chromatogram at 264 nm, showing the main compounds present in crude HMF.

Table S4: different samples from purification process FDCA.

Samples	FDCA (Mm)	Volume (mL)	FDCA (μmol)	FDCA (%)
Final reaction solution	33.9	17.8	600.7	100
Precipitate supernatant	5.8	19.8	114.1	19
Wash acid water	0.9	53.3	45.2	7.5
Solubilized in ethanol	8.1	53.3	432.2	72

Figure S7: Schematic representation of the FDCA purification process following enzymatic conversion using crude HMF.

Equations used for GWP calculations (Domínguez de María, 2024) and E-factor:

GWP_{mass}

$$\text{GWP (water(wwtp))} = \frac{0.073 \cdot \% \text{watertreated}}{\text{Yield} \cdot [\text{SL}]} \quad (\text{Eq S1})$$

where %watertreated is the % of water that will be treated in wwtp (i.e., not reused), Yield is the yield of the reaction (%) and [SL] is the substrate loading in kg·L⁻¹.

GWP_{energy}

$$\text{GWP(water(energy))} = \left(\frac{0.037 \cdot \Delta T}{\text{Yield} \cdot [\text{SL}]} \right) + t \cdot \left(\frac{0.0056 \cdot \Delta T}{\text{Yield} \cdot [\text{SL}]} \right) \quad (\text{Eq S2})$$

where, Yield is the yield of the reaction (%), [SL] is the substrate loading in kg·L⁻¹ and ΔT is the temperature difference from 20 °C and the temperature of the system.

Yields (%) were assumed instead of conversions, to make the calculations more consistent considering the total reaction mass that will be treated through de WWTP.

Table S5. Raw data used for GWPs and E-factor calculations.

% water	SL (kg ·L ⁻¹)	Conv (%)	ΔT (°C)	Product mass (kg)	Waste mass (kg)	References
100	0.002	51.5	8	0.00016	0.12983	Yang, 2016
100	0.001	41.5	6	0.00002	0.03997	Yang, 2018
100	0.003	53.1	10	0.00009	0.04990	Rode, 2021
100	0.006	70.6	10	0.00014	0.01785	This study

E-factor

$$E - \text{factor} = \frac{\text{mass of total waste (kg)}}{\text{mass of total product (kg)}} \quad (\text{Eq S3})$$